

THE IMPORTANCE OF ALEXANDER FEINBERG'S WORKS
IN UZBEK LITERATURE

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about Alexander Feinberg, who, despite being a Russian-speaker, was able to find a place in the heart of the Uzbek nation. Covering many aspects of Feinberg's literary heritage, highlighting its importance at the same time, it is intended to inculcate the main ideas of the poet's work to the readers. His writings come to the hands of Uzbek readers, he translated rare examples of Uzbek literature into Russian, that is, his translation skills are also interpreted. Feinberg's works are promoted among young artists in order to spread it more widely.

Keywords: "Chig'ir" poetic collection, unique heritage, national poet, nationality, humanity, translation activity.

One of the brightest stars in the sky of Uzbek poets is Alexander Feinberg Arkadevich. A skilled poet and translator who left an indelible mark on literature lovers, a favorite writer who has a place in the hearts of Uzbek and Russian book lovers, was born on November 2, 1939 in Tashkent. His father was Arkady Lvovich, his mother was Anastasia Alexandrovna. The poet was born after his parents moved from Novosibirsk. His childhood was spent on the former Zhukovsky street. After that, he lived and created his works in Tashkent all his life. After completing seven years of school like ordinary children, Feinberg entered the Tashkent topographical college. After graduating from the topographical college, he went to Tajikistan for military service. Having completed his military service, he graduated from Tashkent University (now Tashkent State National University) from the journalism department of the faculty of philology and worked for a large number of students. For several years, he led the seminars of young writers in Tashkent. He worked as a consultant in the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan, and was also one of its active members. In 1961, Inna Glebovna Koval and Alexander Arkadevich Feinberg got married.

He entered Uzbek poetry in the second half of the last century. His poems and collections were read hand in hand, songs were sung based on his texts, and his works were translated into Uzbek. Feinberg is the author of more than 15 poetry collections, more than 20 cartoons and prose works. "Etude" (1967), "Sonia" (1969), "Poems" (1977), "Distant Bridges", "Response" (1982), "Short Wave" (1983), "Free Sonnets" (1990) are among them. Based on the poet's screenplays "My brother", "Caught in

Kandahar”, “Criminals and acquittals” and other films were created at the “Uzbekfilm” film studio. His rare works were published in the press of foreign countries such as Canada and Israel and were loved by readers. In the epic “Rubai Tori”, the Uzbek teahouse is skillfully depicted, which belongs to his series of comic works.

Alexander Feinberg is also skilled in the field of translation and has translated the works of many Uzbek poets for Russian readers. He skilfully translated the poems and epics of famous writers of Uzbek poetry, A.Navoi, E.Vakhidov, A.Oripov, O.Matjon into Russian. The collection of translations of works of Uzbek poets entitled “Aqqushlar gala” published in Tashkent and the poem “Rebellion of Spirits” by Erkin Vahidov published in Moscow are the double peaks of Feinberg's translation work. Most of Feinberg’s artistic heritage was translated into Uzbek by Rustam Musurman. The writer’s poems, which are unique masterpieces, were published in magazines such as “Youth”, “Change”, “New World”, “New Volga”. Feinberg travelled around the country as a geologist and fell in love with its beautiful and unique nature. It was during this period that his first book, “The bicycle lane” was published. As a real poet respects Uzbekistan as his motherland, his love, gratitude, humanity, and nationalism are clearly reflected in his heritage. Feinberg’s contribution to the development of multinational Uzbek literature has been well-received by the government. The People’s Poet of Uzbekistan Alexander Arkadevich Feinberg was awarded with the Pushkin Medal a year before his death, i.e. in 2008. It is a pity that the Uzbek Russian poet at heart died in Tashkent in 2009. A two-volume collection of works collected by the artist was published after his death. In order to perpetuate the memory of Feinberg in Uzbekistan, a statue of Feinberg was erected along with other classical writers in the Alley of Writers. A special scholarship named after Feinberg was established in order to promote literary creativity. The memory of Alexander Feinberg is always alive in the heart of the Uzbek nation, his incomparable contribution to the development of our literature, his unforgettable works are a real treasure for Uzbek readers.

REFERENCES:

1. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/aleksandr-faynbergning-yorqin-xotirasi>
2. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aleksandr_Faynberg
3. <https://aroblar.uz/uz/people/fajnberg-aleksandr-arkadevich>
4. <https://aroblar.uz/uz/people/fajnberg-aleksandr-arkadevich>